

PANGEO multidisciplinary test case for Earth and Environment Big data analysis in FAIR-EASE Infra-EOSC project

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Earth observation and modelling is a major challenge for research and a necessity for environmental and socio-economic applications. It requires voluminous and heterogeneous data from distributed and domain-dependent data sources, managed separately by various national and European infrastructures.

In a context of unprecedented data wealth and growth, new challenges emerge to enable inter-comparison, inter-calibration and comprehensive studies and uses of earth system and environmental data.

To this end, the FAIR-EASE project aims to provide integrated and interoperable services through the European Open Science Cloud to facilitate the discovery, access and analysis of large volumes of heterogeneous data from distributed sources and from different domains and disciplines of Earth system science.

This presentation will explain how the PANGEO stack will be used within FAIR EASE to improve data access, interpolation and analysis, but will also explore its integration with existing services (e.g. Galaxy) and underlying IT infrastructure to serve multidisciplinary research uses.

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